

Effect of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) on Science Education Students' Achievements in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the academic achievements of Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke (FUO), Bayelsa State. Guided by two research questions and hypotheses, a quasi-experimental design was employed. The population comprised 434 first-year Science Education students, from which a sample of 360 was selected using convenience sampling. The Introduction to Science Education Achievement Test (ISEAT), a 30-item multiple-choice test, served as the instrument for data collection, and its reliability was confirmed with a Kuder-Richardson formula 21 index of .74. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to answer the research questions, while t-tests at a .05 significance level tested the hypotheses. Results indicated a significant improvement in the mean scores of students exposed to generative AI compared to the control group. Additionally, male students showed greater academic achievement gains with the use of generative AI. The study concludes that integrating generative AI into teaching significantly enhances students' academic performance and promotes gender-responsive pedagogy. Based on the above findings, it was recommended that; educational institutions should integrate generative AI tools into their curriculum to foster improved academic outcomes and address gender disparities in learning amongst others.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence, Science Education, Academic Achievements, FUO, Gender-Responsive Pedagogy

Introduction

The rapid advancement of technology has profoundly impacted various sectors, including education. Among these technological innovations, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool with the potential to transform teaching and learning processes. Generative AI refers to AI systems that can generate new content, such as text, images, and music, based on the data they have been trained on. This capability presents unique opportunities for enhancing educational experiences and outcomes.

Artificial Intelligence (AI), according to Gosh et al (2021), is a branch of Computer Science dedicated to creating systems that emulate human behavior to enhance performance in various scientific and technological fields. The primary objectives of AI include replicating human

intelligence, solving complex, knowledge-intensive tasks, and developing machines capable of performing activities that traditionally require human intelligence. Additionally, AI aims to create systems that can learn autonomously.

One of the most innovative areas of AI is Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI). GAI is a form of artificial intelligence that leverages machine learning and deep learning techniques to create new data. Unlike traditional AI tasks such as classification and regression, generative AI autonomously produces new data, including images, music, and text. The cornerstone of generative AI is the generative model, which learns the distribution of existing data and generates new data that resembles the original dataset. The applications of generative AI are diverse, spanning image creation, natural language processing, and music composition (Lim et al., 2022). Generative AI, encompassing technologies like GPT-4, ChatGPT, DALL-E, MidJourney, MusicLM, and CodeX, has revolutionized content creation across text, images, music, and code (Samuelson, 2023; Bank, 2023; Selker, 2023). These AI models not only enhance creativity but also offer personalized learning experiences and support diverse applications in various media industries (Ebert et al, 2023). From generating realistic human faces with StyleGAN to assisting in dynamic storytelling with AI Dungeon, generative AI tools have rapidly gained widespread usage and the potential to boost productivity in fields like education. GAI has indeed emerged as a powerful tool with the potential to revolutionize teaching and learning processes in education. By leveraging large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT and diffusion model image and video generators, AI technologies can provide educators and students with access to vast measure of information, create innovative learning materials efficiently, and enhance instructional resources (Owan et al, 2023; Adiguzel et al, 2023). These AI tools offer benefits such as personalized feedback for students, improved assessment accuracy, and the ability to adapt teaching strategies to meet individual student needs, ultimately leading to better educational outcomes (Johri et al, 2023). However, the integration of AI in education also poses challenges related to ethics, practicality, data privacy, and fairness, which need to be addressed through responsible and ethical use of AI technologies (Menekse, 2023; Yu, et al, 2023). Overall, the application of generative AI in education holds immense promise for transforming learning experiences and improving educational outcomes for students.

In recent years, there has been a growing research interest in the application of generative artificial intelligence in the field of education, especially since the release of Chat GPT in November 2022, which brought the concept of generative AI to the public attention and sparked increasing interest in its potential impact on education. This necessitated the curiosity to explore how this advanced AI technology can be harnessed to enhance teaching and learning processes. With the increasing popularity of mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets, along with advancements in network technology, many educational applications based on generative AI technology have emerged. These applications offer students convenient learning methods, enhancing their understanding and mastery of knowledge. Additionally, some applications leverage generative AI to provide real-time, intelligent processes for personalized teaching. These systems can automatically adjust the

difficulty and content of courses based on a student's learning performance and level, delivering tailored learning tasks and exercises (Khosravi et al, 2022). Furthermore, these systems can generate relevant learning resources and paths based on a student's habits and needs, promoting more efficient and purposeful learning. They also offer real-time feedback and suggestions to help students correct errors and improve their learning strategies. Moreover, intelligent teaching systems can interact with parents and teachers, providing insights into students' learning progress and performance to enable more comprehensive and effective educational support (Yu et al, 2023). For instance, Knewton's Adaptive Learning Platform utilizes AI technology to analyze students' learning data—such as learning speed, mastery of knowledge points, and error rates—to understand their needs and weaknesses. It then generates personalized course content and teaching plans accordingly (Lim et al., 2022). If a student struggles with a particular concept, the platform adjusts the course content and difficulty, offering more detailed explanations and exercises. Additionally, it provides real-time feedback and suggestions based on the student's progress and performance, helping them better grasp knowledge and skills. Through this personalized teaching approach, the Knewton platform enhances learning efficiency and effectiveness, making education more flexible and impactful (Yu et al, 2023).

Science Education, which encompasses the teaching and learning processes that aim to instill scientific knowledge, critical thinking, and investigative skills in students at various levels, from early childhood to adulthood (Oliveira et al, 2020). In this case, complex concepts and problem-solving skills are paramount, generative AI offers promising applications. It can provide personalized learning experiences, adapt to individual students' needs, and offer instant feedback, thereby fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment. The integration of generative AI in education aligns with contemporary pedagogical trends that emphasize active learning, student-centered approaches, and the development of higher-order thinking skills.

Generative artificial intelligence, exemplified by ChatGPT, Copilot and Gemini are being integrated into Science Education, offering transformative potential but also raising ethical concerns. ChatGPT can assist educators in designing science units, rubrics, and quizzes (Cooper, 2023), potentially revolutionizing pedagogy. However, its tendency to disregard facts and generate fake information poses risks of misinformation (Shaw et al, 2023). Predictive estimates suggest a shift towards creativity-oriented education, increased AI technology use, and new legal and ethical standards in education due to generative AI integration (Konstantinova et al, 2023). In medical education, similar concerns arise, emphasizing the need for cautious use and understanding of AI limitations in conveying accurate information and avoiding bias (Ahmed et al, 2023). Academic institutions vary in responses to large language models like ChatGPT, with some banning them and others embracing their potential in education (Carl and Christian, 2023). Educators must critically evaluate AI-generated resources, prioritize critical thinking, and model responsible use to harness the benefits of generative AI while mitigating its risks in science education.

Science education, in particular, stands to benefit significantly from the integration of generative AI. Traditional teaching methods often struggle to engage students and meet the diverse needs of

learners. According to Yu, (2023), generative AI can provide personalized learning experiences, create dynamic and interactive educational content, and offer immediate feedback, thereby addressing some of the critical challenges faced in Science Education.

Despite the growing interest in AI applications in education, empirical studies specifically examining the effects of generative AI on students' achievements in the context of Science Education in Nigerian universities, remain limited. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating how generative AI influences the academic performance of Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke. Moreover, there is a need to understand how generative AI affects different demographic groups, such as male and female students, to ensure that educational technologies promote equity and inclusivity. By investigating these aspects, this study seeks to provide insights into the effectiveness of generative AI as a tool for improving educational outcomes and addressing gender disparities in Science Education.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the increasing integration of technology in education, the academic performance of science education students at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, remains a significant concern. Traditional teaching methods often fail to adequately engage students or address their individual learning needs, leading to suboptimal learning outcomes. Moreover, disparities in academic achievement between male and female students persist, highlighting the need for more inclusive and effective educational strategies.

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize Science Education by providing personalized and interactive learning experiences. However, there is a lack of empirical evidence on its effectiveness in improving students' achievement in the context of Nigerian universities. Specifically, it is unclear whether the application of generative AI can enhance the academic performance of Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke and whether it can address gender disparities in learning outcomes.

This study sought to address this gap by investigating the effects of generative AI on the academic achievements of Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke. By examining both overall performance and gender-related differences, the research aimed to provide insights into the potential of generative AI as a tool for improving educational outcomes and promoting gender equity in Science Education.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the effects of generative artificial intelligence on Science Education students' achievements in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. In specific terms, the study was intended to determine the;

1. Mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence method and the lecture method;
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and post-test?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental Group)?

Hypotheses

The following two hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

Ho₁ There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence strategy (experimental Group) and the lecture method (Control Group).

Ho₂ There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence strategy (Experimental Group).

Method

This study utilized a quasi-experimental design to investigate the effects of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) on the academic achievements of Science Education students in Introduction to Science Education (FUO-SED 101) at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The design was chosen to compare the achievement of students exposed to GAI with those receiving traditional instruction. The population for this study consisted of 434 first-year Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke. A sample of 360 students was selected through convenience sampling, ensuring a manageable and representative subset of the population. The Introduction to Science Education Achievement Test (ISEAT), a 30-item multiple-choice test, was employed as the primary instrument for data collection. The ISEAT was designed to measure students' understanding and knowledge of Introductory Science Education concepts.

The reliability of the instrument was established using the Kuder-Richardson formula 21, yielding an index of .74, indicating acceptable reliability for the study. Participants were divided into two groups: an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was exposed to generative AI tools (ChatGPT, DALL-E, Copilot and Gemini) integrated into their learning activities, while the control group received traditional teaching methods. Both groups were subjected to a pre-test in week 1, using the ISEAT to ensure comparability. The treatment for the experimental group involved exposing students to the use of each GAI tool within a period of 1 week. In week 2, the students were introduced to use ChatGPT in defining the concept of Science Education and its sub-fields on their own mobile devices. In week 3, the students were taught how to use DALL-E in creating visual contents relating to science topics e.g., the process of science. Copilot was introduced in week 4 to explain the concept of Scientific Literacy. While in week 5,

students were introduced to the use of guides and procedure obtained from Gemini to carrying out any entrepreneurial projects of their choice e.g., liquid soap, perfume, cleaning agent and shoe making. The control group continued with just the lecture method of instruction, including textbook assignments.

In week 6, both groups were subjected to a post-test using the ISEAT. The mean and standard deviation of the pre-test and post-test scores were calculated to assess the effect of the intervention. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) to answer the research questions. Therefore, the entire study covered a period of 6 weeks of instructions on both groups. To test the null hypotheses, t-tests were conducted at a .05 significance level to determine if there were significant differences between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental and control groups. Additionally, gender differences in academic achievement gains were analyzed to examine the impact of generative AI on male and female students. Findings revealed that integrating generative AI into the teaching of Introduction to Science Education significantly enhanced students' academic achievements. This is because, the experimental group demonstrated higher mean post-test scores compared to the control group, validating the effectiveness of generative AI in improving learning outcomes. Results from the analysis indicated that male students benefited more from the use of generative AI, with greater gains in academic performance compared to female students. This suggests that while generative AI positively impacts all students, it may be particularly effective in addressing the learning needs of male students.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using lecture method (Control Group) in both pre-test and post-test?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Students in the Experimental and Control Groups in both Pre-test and Post-test

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)
Experimental Group	189	28.21	2.14	36.32	3.29
Control Group	171	27.64	2.03	35.48	2.19

Data on Table 1 indicated that at pre-test, the achievement mean score for experimental group was 28.21 with a standard deviation of 2.14. The mean achievement score for the experimental group at post-test was 36.32 with a standard deviation of 3.29. For the control group, at pre-test, the achievement mean score was 27.64 with a corresponding standard deviation of 2.03. The mean

achievement score in the control group at post-test was 35.48 with a standard deviation of 2.19. The standard deviations for both groups showed that the scores of the students were more clustered around the mean with lecture method than with the Generative Artificial Intelligence. This is an indication that students in the experimental group achieved higher than those in the control group considering their higher mean achievement scores at posttest.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental Group)?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean ($\bar{x}$)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Male	57	28.49	3.06	38.39	4.37
Female	132	28.27	3.19	36.29	3.26

From the results presented in Table 2, male students in the experimental group had pre-test mean achievement score and standard deviation of 28.49 and 3.06, while their post-test mean achievement score and standard deviation were 38.39 and 4.37. Female students in the experimental group had pre-test mean achievement score and standard deviation of 28.27 and 3.19, while their post-test mean achievement score and standard deviation was 36.29 and 3.26 respectively. The standard deviation is an indication that the individual scores of the female students are more clustered around the mean than those of their male counterparts that had more extreme scores. This implies that the use of Generative Artificial Intelligence is effective in enhancing the teaching and learning of Introduction to Science Education in favour of the male students. It is also an indication that male students recorded higher achievement than their female counterparts in the experimental group.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental group) and those taught using lecture method (Control group).

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Introduction to Science Education using Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using lecture method (Control Group)

Group	n	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Experimental	189	36.32	3.29	358	.001	H ₀₁ is rejected
Control	171	35.48	2.19			

Data in Table 3 showed that at 358 degree of freedom, the p-value was .001. This shows that the p-value is less than .05 level of significance set for this study, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean ratings of students in both experimental and control groups on the effect of Generative Artificial Intelligence strategy on students' academic achievement when taught Introduction to Science Education.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence strategy (Experimental Group).

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Introduction to Science Education using generative artificial intelligence strategy

Group	n	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	p-value	Decision
Male Students	57	38.39	4.37	187	.003	H ₀₂ is rejected
Female Students	132	36.29	3.26			

Data in Table 4 showed that at 187 degree of freedom, the p-value was .003. This revealed that the p-value is less than .05 level of significance set for this study, hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the effect of generative artificial intelligence strategy on students' academic achievement when taught Introduction to Science Education.

Discussion

The findings of this study, which demonstrated significant positive effects of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) on the academic achievements of Science Education students exposed to GAI tools corroborates findings from previous studies that highlight the educational benefits of AI technologies. For instance, Holmes et al. (2019) found that AI-enhanced learning environments can lead to improved student engagement and higher academic achievement. Similarly, a study by Luckin et al. (2016) reported that AI-driven personalized learning systems effectively address individual student needs, leading to better learning outcomes.

Generative AI tools such as ChatGPT and DALL-E facilitate interactive and personalized learning experiences, which are necessary for students' engagements. The work by Diao et al. (2019) emphasized that AI-driven personalization helps tailor educational content to individual learning styles and paces, thereby enhancing understanding and retention. The present study's findings support this, as students in the experimental group exhibited significantly higher post-test scores, suggesting that GAI can successfully personalize and enrich the learning experience.

The greater academic gains observed among male students exposed to GAI resonate with some existing literature while contrasting with other studies. For instance, Hattie (2009) suggested that

interactive and technology-enhanced learning environments often cater more to male students, who may be more engaged by such tools. However, it is important to note that other studies, such as those by OECD (2015), indicated that the gender gap in technology usage and performance is complex and context-dependent.

The findings that male students showed more significant improvement than female students highlight the need for a gender-responsive approach to implementing GAI in education. This aligns with the research by UNESCO (2019), which emphasizes that while educational technologies hold promise, they must be designed and implemented in ways that are inclusive and sensitive to gender differences. Future studies could explore how to tailor GAI tools to support female students better and ensure equitable benefits.

The positive effects of GAI observed in this study is consistent with global trends in AI integration in education. For example, the AI in Education Market Report (2021) projected significant growth in AI applications in educational settings, driven by their potential to enhance learning outcomes and provide personalized learning experiences.

However, while the overall findings align with broader research, it is important to consider the unique context of Federal University Otuoke. Factors such as local educational practices, availability of resources, and students' familiarity with technology can influence the effectiveness of GAI. Studies in different cultural and educational contexts, such as those by Miao and Holmes (2021), posited that local adaptation is requisite to the successful implementation of AI in education.

Conclusion

The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the use of generative AI in education. The significant improvement in academic achievements and the observed gender differences in learning outcomes underscore the potential of GAI to enhance educational experiences while also strengthening the need for thoughtful, and inclusive implementation strategies. By building on existing empirical works, this study provides valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers aiming to leverage AI to improve educational outcomes in related fields.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Tertiary institutions should adopt and implement gender-responsive AI tools and pedagogical strategies that will cater to the diverse learning needs of both male and female students, ensuring that educational technologies do not inadvertently favor one gender over the other.
2. To maximize the benefits of generative AI in education, universities should invest in ongoing professional development for all academic staff. Training programs should focus

on equipping lecturers with the skills and knowledge to effectively integrate AI tools into their teaching practices.

3. Lecturers should be familiar with the capabilities and limitations of AI technologies, understand how to leverage them to personalize learning experiences, and be adept at using data from these tools to inform instruction.
4. Training should include strategies for creating an inclusive classroom environment that benefits all students, regardless of gender.

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